

1 Distinct Sensitivities of Extratropical Low Cloud Regimes to Cloud Controlling Factors Across
2 Multiple Timescale

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21 in this Word file and for publication; but only one corresponding author is allowed in our editorial system.)

22 **Key Points:**

- 23
- 24 • A The seasonal cycle of Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC) is not a robust proxy for
25 long-term feedback due to timescale-dependent responses to stability.
 - 26 • Inversion strength controls LBCs but responds differently to warming on seasonal
27 (dynamic) versus interannual (thermodynamic) timescales.
 - 28 • Uncertainty in cloud feedback arises primarily from parameterized cloud sensitivities
29 to vertical velocity and humidity, not large-scale circulation changes.

30 Abstract

31 Extratropical marine low cloud feedback remains a primary source of uncertainty in
32 estimating Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS). Recent studies have proposed using the
33 observed seasonal cycle of low clouds as an "emergent constraint" to reduce this uncertainty.
34 However, the validity of such constraints relies on the assumption that the physical mechanisms
35 governing seasonal variations are consistent with those driving long-term climate feedback. In
36 this study, we investigate the dominant physical processes driving extratropical low cloud
37 variability by decomposing clouds into three regimes based on cloud-top height: Multi-layer
38 clouds (MLC), Upper boundary-layer clouds (UBC), and Lower boundary-layer clouds (LBC).
39 Using CloudSat-CALIPSO observations and CMIP6 model outputs (CESM2 and MPI-ESM),
40 we quantify the sensitivity of these regimes to key Cloud Controlling Factors (CCFs)—
41 including Sea Surface Temperature (SST), Estimated Inversion Strength (EIS), relative
42 humidity (RH_{700}), and vertical velocity ($OMEGA_{700}$)—across seasonal and interannual
43 timescales. We find that while MLC and UBC exhibit consistent responses across timescales,
44 the response of LBC to surface temperature is inconsistent between seasonal and interannual
45 timescales. This breakdown is mechanistically driven by the differing responses of
46 tropospheric stability (EIS) to surface warming on different timescales: seasonally, EIS is
47 controlled by dynamic subsidence, whereas interannually, it is modulated by the
48 thermodynamic response to widespread ocean warming. Consequently, the seasonal cycle of
49 LBC is not a robust proxy for its long-term feedback. Furthermore, a decomposition of the
50 cloud feedback spread reveals that inter-model uncertainty arises primarily from the cloud
51 sensitivity term ($\frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF}$) rather than the large-scale state changes ($\frac{dLCF}{dT_s}$). Specifically, the
52 divergent model simulations of cloud sensitivities to dynamic ($OMEGA_{700}$) and
53 thermodynamic (RH_{700}) drivers are identified as the dominant sources of spread. These results
54 highlight the necessity of improving physical parameterizations of cloud-turbulence
55 interactions to reduce uncertainty in climate projections.

56

57 Plain Language Summary

58

59 Marine low clouds play a crucial role in cooling the Earth by reflecting sunlight.
60 Predicting how these clouds will change as the planet warms is difficult, so scientists often
61 look at how clouds change with seasons (e.g., from winter to summer) to infer their future
62 behavior. This method assumes that the physical rules governing clouds are the same across
63 different timescales. In this study, we separated low clouds into three types based on their

64 height. We found that for the lowest clouds (Lower Boundary-layer Clouds, or LBC), the
65 "seasonal rule" does not apply to long-term warming. This is because the atmospheric stability
66 (the "lid" that traps these clouds) reacts differently to temperature changes on seasonal scales
67 compared to year-to-year warming. Consequently, simply observing the seasons cannot predict
68 the future of these specific clouds. Furthermore, we compared different climate models and
69 found that their disagreements mainly stem from how they simulate the clouds' internal
70 sensitivity to air movement and moisture, rather than differences in the predicted weather
71 patterns themselves. Our findings suggest that to improve climate predictions, model
72 developers need to focus on refining the physics of how clouds react to their immediate
73 environment.

74

75 **1 Introduction**

76 Developing robust policies for climate mitigation and adaptation requires precise
77 projections of global temperature increases driven by greenhouse gas (GHG) accumulation.
78 Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS)—the stabilized increase in global mean surface
79 temperature following a doubling of atmospheric CO₂—remains a fundamental metric in this
80 regard. Despite decades of research, the range of ECS estimates within Global Climate Models
81 (GCMs) has persistently spanned approximately 1.5 to 4.5 K (Charney et al., 1979; Meehl et
82 al., 2020). This uncertainty has notably widened in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
83 Phase 6 (CMIP6), where estimates range from 1.8 to 5.6 K, driven largely by increases in both
84 the mean and the upper bounds of sensitivity (Zelinka et al., 2020). Cloud feedback,
85 particularly those associated with low-level clouds, have been identified as the primary driver
86 of this expanded inter-model spread (Zelinka et al., 2020). Consequently, emergent
87 constraints—methods that link observable present-day climate variables to future
88 projections—have gained traction as a vital tool for narrowing these uncertainties.

89

90 The influence of cloud feedback on ECS variability is well documented (Cess et al.,
91 1990; Sherwood et al., 2020; Stephens, 2005). Clouds play a dual role in the Earth's radiation
92 budget: they induce warming by trapping outgoing longwave radiation and cooling by
93 reflecting incoming solar radiation. The Net Cloud Radiative Effect (CRE) depends heavily on

94 specific cloud characteristics, including cloud-top height (CTH), optical thickness (COT),
95 thermodynamic phase, and fractional coverage (Su & Du, 2024). In a warming climate, shifts
96 in these properties can either exacerbate or mitigate temperature rise. Low-level clouds are
97 particularly critical due to their dominant cooling effect; changes in their coverage could trigger
98 significant positive or negative feedbacks. However, determining the sign and magnitude of
99 low-cloud feedback remains a major challenge. GCMs struggle to accurately represent these
100 processes due to gaps in physical understanding and the sub-grid nature of cloud dynamics,
101 leading to divergent CRE responses and, by extension, a wide range of ECS estimates. A strong
102 correlation exists between shortwave low-cloud feedback and ECS, where positive feedback is
103 associated with higher sensitivity. Given that low clouds (typically defined with tops below ~3
104 km or ~680 hPa) provide substantial radiative cooling, any reduction in their extent or opacity
105 could disrupt the top-of-atmosphere (TOA) energy balance and significantly impact surface
106 temperatures.

107

108 Resolving the uncertainties surrounding low-cloud feedback is hindered by limitations
109 inherent in current research methodologies (Ceppi & Nowack, 2021). Theoretical models
110 currently lack the precision for quantitative prediction, while the coarse resolution of GCMs
111 prevents the explicit simulation of small-scale cloud processes, resulting in inconsistent
112 feedback strengths across models (Ceppi et al., 2017; Zelinka et al., 2020). While high-
113 resolution models offer improved accuracy for fine-scale dynamics, their computational
114 demands make them impractical for global, centennial-scale projections (Schneider et al.,
115 2017). Furthermore, observational constraints are often restricted to specific meteorological
116 regimes, such as tropical subsidence zones (Brient & Schneider, 2016; Klein et al., 2017;
117 McCoy et al., 2017; Myers & Norris, 2016; Qu et al., 2015). These estimates are further

118 complicated by limited satellite data records and the challenge of disentangling long-term
119 warming responses from natural climate variability.

120

121 Low clouds in both the subtropics (0–30°N/S) and the extratropics (30–60°N/S) are
122 major contributors to global cloud feedback (Gettelman & Sherwood, 2016; Klein et al., 2017).
123 While subtropical clouds have been studied extensively (Bony & Dufresne, 2005), the
124 significance of extratropical low-cloud feedback has only recently been prioritized. Zelinka et
125 al. (2020) highlighted that enhanced positive feedback in these regions is a primary factor
126 explaining the higher ECS values in CMIP6 compared to CMIP5. Additionally, inaccuracies
127 in simulating mixed-phase clouds in the extratropics may lead to overestimated negative cloud-
128 phase feedbacks, thereby artificially suppressing ECS in some models (Bodas-Salcedo et al.,
129 2019; Frey & Kay, 2018; Gettelman & Sherwood, 2016; Tan et al., 2016). The complex, multi-
130 layered structure of extratropical cloud systems further complicates retrieval from both active
131 and passive satellites (Haynes et al., 2011; Marchand et al., 2009; Sourdeval et al., 2016). These
132 observational and structural challenges necessitate a focused investigation into extratropical
133 cloud feedbacks. Marine low clouds cover vast areas of the global oceans and play a critical
134 role in Earth's energy budget by reflecting incoming solar radiation. The response of these
135 clouds to global warming—known as low cloud feedback—remains one of the largest sources
136 of uncertainty in Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS) among the latest generation of Global
137 Climate Models (CMIP6)¹. In particular, the feedback from extratropical low clouds (30°-
138 60°N/S) has been identified as a key contributor to the increased ECS and inter-model spread
139 in CMIP6 compared to CMIP5.

140

141 To constrain this uncertainty, recent studies have sought "emergent constraints"—
 142 observable relationships in the current climate that correlate with future projections. The
 143 seasonal cycle of low clouds has been proposed as a promising candidate. The underlying
 144 hypothesis is timescale invariance: the physical mechanisms driving cloud variability on
 145 seasonal timescales are assumed to be similar to those operating under long-term climate
 146 change. However, conflicting results have challenged this assumption. For instance, Jiang et
 147 al. (2023) reported a winter maximum in extratropical low cloud fraction (ELCF) associated
 148 with positive feedback, whereas Furtado et al. (2023) found a summer maximum associated
 149 with negative feedback.

150

151 In our companion paper (Du et al., in prep), we resolved this phenomenological
 152 discrepancy by introducing a physics-based cloud classification that separates low clouds into
 153 Multi-layer (MLC), Upper Boundary-layer (UBC), and Lower Boundary-layer (LBC) regimes.
 154 We showed that bulk definitions of "low cloud" conflate these distinct regimes, which have
 155 opposing seasonal cycles. In this study, we go beyond the seasonal cycle to rigorously test the
 156 timescale invariance assumption and identify the physical drivers of inter-model spread. We
 157 specifically address the following questions:

- 158 1. Do the sensitivities of distinct cloud regimes (MLC, UBC, LBC) to meteorological drivers
 159 remain consistent across seasonal and interannual timescales?
- 160 2. What physical mechanisms (e.g., stability vs. dynamics) drive the breakdown of timescale
 161 invariance for specific cloud types?
- 162 3. Does the inter-model spread in cloud feedback arise from differences in the large-scale
 163 environment ($\frac{dLCF}{dT_s}$) or from the cloud parameterizations' response to that environment
 164 ($\frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF}$)?

165 **2 Data and Methods**

166 **2.1. Data Sources and Processing**

167 Our analysis focuses on the period from 1986 to 2014 for model simulations, and from
168 2006 to 2011 for satellite observations and reanalyses. We utilize daily fields of cloud fraction
169 (cl), surface temperature (tas), sea surface temperature (tos), vertical velocity (OMEGA),
170 temperature (T), and relative humidity (rh), using the CMIP variable naming convention. To
171 ensure a consistent and physically meaningful comparison across all datasets, the vertical levels
172 of all model outputs were standardized to a common pressure coordinate system. The CESM2
173 simulation was conducted specifically for this study. Its output was natively provided on 32
174 standard pressure levels. In contrast, the daily data from other CMIP6 models were typically
175 archived on model-specific hybrid sigma-pressure coordinates. To eliminate inter-model
176 discrepancies arising from differing vertical coordinates, we first calculated the corresponding
177 pressure at each model level for these datasets. Subsequently, cloud fraction variables were
178 vertically interpolated using linear interpolation in log-pressure space to the same set of 32
179 pressure levels as the CESM2 output. This crucial step guarantees that the vertical structure of
180 cloud fields is compared consistently and accurately across all models and observations.

181

182 **2.1.1. Climate Model Simulations**

183

184 **2.1.1.1 CMIP6 Models**

185 Daily averaged output from MPI-ESM model was selected for this study. All selected
186 models followed the Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project (AMIP) protocol to ensure
187 experimental consistency. The relatively small ensemble size is a direct result of the limited

188 availability of daily output for the required cloud and dynamical variables across the full
189 CMIP6 archive.

190

191 To enable a robust comparison between the CESM2 simulation and the CMIP6 models,
192 a uniform temporal processing procedure was applied. First, a 5-day running mean was
193 calculated from the daily data. In this averaging process, if a specific cloud type was not present
194 on a given day, its cloud fraction was treated as zero. Subsequently, monthly means were
195 derived from these 5-day averaged values to analyze the seasonal cycle. This two-step approach
196 ensures a consistent and comparable analysis of the cloud seasonal cycles across all models,
197 despite their differing native temporal outputs.

198

199 To ensure all model analyses represent a fully spun up and equilibrated climate state,
200 and to maintain temporal consistency across the ensemble, the analysis period for all climate
201 models (including the dedicated CESM2 run) is unified from 1986 to 2014. This start date
202 accounts for the 6-year spin-up period required for the CESM2 simulation to stabilize.

203

204 **2.1.1.2 CESM2 (Community Earth System Model version 2)**

205 The atmospheric simulations were conducted using the Community Atmosphere Model
206 version 6 (CAM6), the atmospheric component of the Community Earth System Model version
207 2.1.5 (CESM2), developed at the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), which
208 is funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) (Bogenschutz et al., 2018; Gettelman et
209 al., 2018). The model was run following the Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project
210 (AMIP) protocols, prescribed with observational sea surface temperatures and sea ice coverage

211 from 1979 to 2014 (Huang et al., 2021; Rayner et al., 2003). Monthly boundary condition data
212 were linearly interpolated in time to generate daily forcing inputs. The modeling framework
213 was also forced with temporally evolving aerosol emissions and greenhouse gas concentrations
214 (including CO₂) to maintain fidelity with historical atmospheric composition.

215

216 The numerical experiments adopted the standard CAM6 scientific resolution: the
217 horizontal discretization featured a 0.94° latitude × 1.25° longitude grid, while the vertical
218 structure employed 32 hybrid sigma-pressure layers extending to 2.26 hPa. Output datasets
219 encompassed both static and dynamic prognostic variables, archived at a 6-hour temporal
220 resolution. The horizontal and vertical grid specifications remained unchanged throughout the
221 simulations for consistency.

222

223 **2.1.2. Observational and Reanalysis Datasets**

224 **2.1.2.1 CloudSat-CALIPSO (Active Sensor)**

225 To accurately characterize cloud vertical structure, this study utilized the CloudSat-
226 CALIPSO (C-C) cloud classification product. Our primary dataset for cloud vertical structure
227 is calculated from the level-2 data streams 2B-GEOPROF and 2B-GEOPROF-LIDAR. The
228 2B-GEOPROF product provides a confidence-graded hydrometeor mask from CloudSat's
229 Cloud Profiling Radar (CPR), while the 2B-GEOPROF-LIDAR product contains CALIPSO's
230 lidar cloud mask resampled to the CloudSat footprint.

231

232 These foundational data are integrated into the 2B-CLDCLASS-LIDAR product
233 (version R05), which synergistically combines the CPR on CloudSat and the CALIOP lidar on

234 CALIPSO. This synergistic product offers unparalleled detection of multi-layer and thin clouds
 235 (Mace et al., 2009) and provides a physically based cloud type classification, which is central
 236 to our analysis. We analyzed data from January 2006 to December 2011, excluding the period
 237 after November 2011 due to a battery anomaly that limited CloudSat's operational coverage.

238

239 To conform with the gridding of our climate model data, the native satellite curtain data
 240 were aggregated onto a common global grid. The cloud mask information from the combined
 241 radar-lidar product was first converted into a binary cloud/no-cloud field at each native profile.
 242 These profiles were then spatiotemporally collocated and averaged onto a $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ horizontal
 243 grid at a 6-hourly temporal resolution, matching the output frequency of our model analysis.
 244 For each grid box and time interval, the cloud fraction was calculated as the number of satellite
 245 profiles identified as "cloudy" divided by the total number of observed profiles within that grid
 246 box and time window.

247 **2.1.2.2 ERA5**

248 For other meteorological data, we use the latest ERA5 reanalysis from the European
 249 Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

250

Table 1. Observation data and source

Variable	Data Source
Radiation flux	CERES
Sea Surface Temperature	ERA5
Temperature	ERA5

Vertical Velocity	ERA5
Relative Humidity	ERA5

251 **2.2 Cloud Classification Framework**

252 Following Du et al. (2026; in prep), we classify low clouds based on Cloud Top Height
 253 (CTH) (shown in Figure 1):

- 254 1. Multi-layer clouds (MLC): defined by a cloud top above 700 hPa, these typically include
 255 deep convective systems or cirrus with underlying low clouds.
- 256 2. Upper boundary-layer clouds (UBC): with a cloud top between 850 and 700 hPa, these are
 257 generally composed of thicker cumulus clouds.
- 258 3. Lower boundary-layer clouds (LBC): with a cloud top at or below 850 hPa, these are
 259 primarily stratocumulus clouds formed under boundary-layer inversions.

260

261 Figure 1. Schematic of the three cloud types (Multi-layer Cloud; Upper Boundary Layer Cloud;
 262 Lower Boundary Layer Cloud) (From Du et al., 2026; in prep)

263

264 **2.3 Cloud Controlling Factor (CCF) Decomposition**

265 These studies operate on the premise that tropical low-cloud properties governing
 266 radiative fluxes (including low-cloud fraction and shortwave cloud-radiative effects) exhibit
 267 anomalies ΔC describable through a first order linear Taylor expansion around the
 268 climatology in their controlling factors $x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$:

$$269 \quad \Delta C = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial C(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\partial x_i} \Delta x_i + \text{high order terms} \quad (1)$$

270 where Δx_i 's represent anomalies of controlling factors. Equation (1) defines the partial
 271 derivative $\partial C / \partial x_i$ as quantifying low-cloud sensitivity to controlling factors, maintaining
 272 temporal invariance across scales. This sensitivity persists whether anomalies manifest over
 273 inter-annual, decadal, centennial, or weekly periods, provided durations exceed ~ 2 -3 days -
 274 the maximum adjustment period for marine boundary layer clouds to equilibrate with
 275 exogenous forcings (Bretherton, 1993; Schubert et al., 1979). Temporal averaging diminishes
 276 but cannot fully eliminate cloud-controlling factor disequilibria.

277

278 Table 2 details the primary factors controlling tropical low clouds. For each factor, it
 279 provides the underlying reason for the cloud dependency and references a relevant
 280 observational or large-eddy simulation (LES) study. While substantial research backs each
 281 entry, the level of theoretical grounding and supporting evidence varies considerably among
 282 them. The connection linking stronger low cloud cover to increased inversion strength
 283 represents the most well-established relationship.

284

285

Table 2. Most important cloud controlling factors

Cloud controlling factor	Journal	Physical Meaning
Estimated Inversion Strength (EIS)	Wood & Bretherton, (2006)	The less mixing in inversion makes boundary layer shallower, which cause more humid and more cloud.
Subsidence	Myers & Norris, (2013)	When subsidence reduced, the boundary layer will deeper, and more cloud.
Horizontal advection	Norris & Iacobellis, (2005)	The instability in the interface of surface and atmosphere will cause upward buoyancy flux which cause more cloud.
Free-Troposphere Humidity	Myers & Norris, (2016)	Higher free-tropospheric humidity causes less entrainment drying, which lead to more saturated in boundary layer and more cloud.
Downward longwave radiation	Christensen et al. (2013)	Less downward longwave radiation causes more cloud top radiative cooling,

		which drive more turbulence and more cloud.
Sea Surface Temperature	Qu et al., (2015)	More cloud to produce the entrainment rate for a less efficiency of entrainment when sea surface temperature is colder.
Surface Wind Speed	Brueck et al. (2015)	When surface wind increasing, the wind shear mixing increasing and cause more latent heat flux thus more cloud.

286

287 Determining the precise contribution of individual factors from observations can be
 288 challenging due to covarying relationships, such as that between free-tropospheric relative
 289 humidity and downward longwave radiation. While models can isolate these effects,
 290 observational disentanglement is often inconclusive. Furthermore, consistent large-scale
 291 observational data for some controlling factors is sometimes lacking.

292

293 Table 2 likely includes all major cloud-controlling factors relevant to large-scale
 294 processes. This comprehensiveness stems from its coverage of the principal external variables
 295 found in the boundary layer's energy and moisture budget equations (Stevens & Brenguier,
 296 2009). Nevertheless, the list might omit some recognized elements (e.g., aerosol effects) or
 297 unidentified factors, though these are expected to play only a secondary role in the feedback
 298 response of tropical low clouds to climate warming.

299

300 In this study, we only consider most common used four CCF, which shown in Figure 2.
 301 Generally, when relative humidity at 700 hPa get higher, subsidence weaker (Vertical
 302 velocity used in this study), Estimated inversion strength (EIS) stronger, sea surface
 303 temperature (SST) colder, the low cloud will increase and vice versa.

304
 305 Figure 2. Schematic summary of how low-level clouds respond to changes in each large-scale
 306 meteorological cloud-controlling factor. (From Scott et al., 2020)

307

308 The low cloud fraction (LCF) changes with surface temperature (T_s) change can use first
 309 order Taylor expansion to represent as

310
$$\frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \sum_i \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF_i} \frac{dCCF_i}{dT_s} \quad (2)$$

311 where CCF means cloud controlling factors. We considered four most important CCFs
 312 used in this study, the LCF changes with surface temperature as

$$313 \quad \frac{dLCF}{dT_s} = \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial EIS} \frac{dEIS}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial RH_{700}} \frac{dRH_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial OMEGA_{700}} \frac{dOMGEA_{700}}{dT_s} + \frac{\partial LCF}{\partial SST} \frac{dSST}{dT_s}$$

314 where RH_{700} means relative humidity at 700 hPa, $OMGEA_{700}$ means vertical velocity at
 315 700 hPa. The mult-linear regression method is used to calculate the first term (the partial
 316 derivatives) of the right side of formula 2. And linear regression method to calculate the
 317 second term, how CCFs vary in response to warming.

318

319 **3. Results**

320 **3.1. Distinct Timescale Dependence of Cloud Regime**

321

322 We first examine whether the response of low cloud fractions (LCF) to surface
 323 temperature (T_s) is consistent across seasonal and interannual timescales. This consistency is
 324 the fundamental premise for using the seasonal cycle as an emergent constraint.

325

326 For Multi-layer Clouds (MLC) and Upper Boundary-layer Clouds (UBC), we find a
 327 robust consistency in their sensitivity to surface temperature across timescales. In both
 328 observations (CloudSat) and models (CESM2, MPI-ESM), these cloud regimes generally
 329 exhibit a negative sensitivity to warming (or a winter maximum) in the extratropics on both
 330 seasonal and interannual scales. This suggests that the dominant physical drivers for MLC and
 331 UBC scale relatively linearly from seasonal variations to interannual climate variability.

332

333 Figure 3. Change in low clouds across timescales (Summer – Winter for seasonal timescale; Warm year –
 334 Cold year for inter-annual timescale). Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for MLC,
 335 UBC, and LBC, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale
 336 for the same cloud types.

337

338 However, a striking inconsistency emerges for Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC).
 339 In observations and the CESM2 model, LBC exhibits a strong positive correlation with local
 340 T_s on the seasonal timescale (manifesting as a summer maximum in the extratropic). In stark
 341 contrast, on the interannual timescale, the sensitivity of LBC to T_s becomes weak or negative
 342 over large portions of the global ocean. This "breakdown" of timescale invariance indicates
 343 that the seasonal variability of LBC is physically distinct from its response to interannual
 344 warming, invalidating the use of the LBC seasonal cycle as a direct proxy for long-term
 345 feedback.

346

347 Figure 4. Sensitivity of LBC to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal
 348 timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding
 349 sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

350 3.2 Physical Mechanisms Driving the LBC Inconsistency

351 To explain why LBC violates the timescale invariance assumption, we analyzed the
 352 sensitivities of key Cloud Controlling Factors (CCFs). Our decomposition analysis reveals that
 353 LBC variability is strongly coupled to Estimated Inversion Strength (EIS) ($\frac{\partial LBC}{\partial EIS} > 0$). Therefore,
 354 the inconsistency in LBC must stem from the behavior of EIS.

355 We identified divergent responses of EIS to surface temperature ($\frac{dEIS}{dT_s}$) across timescales:

- 356 • **On the Seasonal Timescale:** EIS is negatively correlated with T_s in the subtropics
 357 and mid-latitudes. This relationship is primarily dynamically driven: during summer,
 358 the subtropical high pressure strengthens, enhancing subsidence, but the surface
 359 temperature rises, leading to a decoupling that decreases stability relative to the
 360 surface warming.
- 361 • **On the Interannual Timescale:** While EIS still generally decreases with warming,
 362 the spatial pattern and magnitude differ significantly. The interannual response is

363 driven by the broad **thermodynamic response** of the troposphere to widespread
 364 ocean warming (e.g., El Niño-like patterns), which destabilizes the lower troposphere
 365 globally but through a different mechanism than the seasonal solar forcing.

366 Since the driver (EIS) responds differently to warming on different timescales, the response
 367 of the cloud regime most sensitive to it (LBC) also shifts. This confirms that the breakdown
 368 of the emergent constraint for LBC is physically rooted in the distinct nature of stability
 369 changes across timescales.

370
 371 Figure 5. Sensitivity of EIS to T_{as} across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the sensitivity at the seasonal
 372 timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show the corresponding
 373 sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

374

375 3.3. Attribution of Inter-Model Spread

376 Finally, we decomposed the inter-model spread in cloud feedback (specifically between high-
 377 ECS CESM2 and low-ECS MPI-ESM) into contributions from the "Cloud Sensitivity" term

378 $\left(\frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF}\right)$ and the "CCF Sensitivity" term $\left(\frac{dCCF}{dT_s}\right)$.

379 Our analysis quantitatively demonstrates that the **Cloud Sensitivity term** dominates the
 380 uncertainty. This implies that the spread is not due to differences in how the models simulate
 381 large-scale circulation changes (e.g., how EIS or ω_{700} change with warming), but rather
 382 due to differences in **how cloud parameterizations respond to those large-scale changes**.

383 We identified two specific parameterization deficiencies:

- 384 1. **Dynamic Sensitivity (ω_{700}):** The spread in the **MLC** regime is driven by
 385 divergent sensitivities to vertical velocity. CESM2 simulates a much stronger
 386 suppression of MLC/UBC under subsidence than MPI-ESM, reflecting differences in
 387 their convective trigger functions and detrainment schemes.

388

389

390 Figure 6. Sensitivity of MLC to vertical velocity at 700 hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the
 391 sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show
 392 the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

393

394 2. **Thermodynamic Sensitivity (RH_{700}):** The spread in the **UBC** regime is driven by
 395 sensitivity to free-tropospheric humidity. The MPI-ESM model severely
 396 underestimates the sensitivity of UBC to RH_{700} compared to observations. This
 397 insensitivity leads to a systematic underestimation of the UBC mean state in MPI-
 398 ESM, which in turn causes the model's total low cloud seasonal cycle to be
 399 erroneously dominated by LBC (the summer-maximum regime).

400

401 Figure 7. Sensitivity of UBC to relative humidity at 700hPa across timescales. Panels (a-c) show the
 402 sensitivity at the seasonal timescale for CloudSat, MPI-ESM, and CESM2, respectively. Panels (d-f) show
 403 the corresponding sensitivity at the inter-annual timescale for the observation or climate model.

404

405 4 Conclusions

406

407 This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the physical mechanisms driving extratropical
 408 marine low cloud variability across seasonal and interannual timescales. By decomposing low
 409 clouds into three distinct regimes—Multi-layer Clouds (MLC), Upper Boundary-layer Clouds

410 (UBC), and Lower Boundary-layer Clouds (LBC)—we have disentangled the conflicting
 411 signals often observed in bulk low-cloud analyses 1. Our main conclusions are as follows:

412 1. Breakdown of Timescale Invariance in LBC: We demonstrate that the "timescale
 413 invariance" assumption—which posits that seasonal cloud responses can constrain
 414 long-term feedbacks—holds for MLC and UBC but fails for the LBC regime. While
 415 MLC and UBC exhibit consistent sensitivities to surface temperature across timescales,
 416 LBC displays a seasonal positive correlation (summer maximum) but a weak or
 417 negative interannual correlation. This inconsistency invalidates the use of the LBC
 418 seasonal cycle as a direct emergent constraint for its climate feedback.

419 2. Thermodynamic vs. Dynamic Drivers of Stability: The breakdown in LBC timescale
 420 invariance is mechanistically driven by the divergent responses of Estimated Inversion
 421 Strength (EIS) to surface warming. On seasonal timescales, EIS in the extratropics is
 422 primarily modulated by dynamic subsidence, leading to a negative correlation with
 423 surface temperature. Conversely, on interannual timescales, widespread ocean warming
 424 thermodynamically destabilizes the lower troposphere, resulting in a global negative
 425 EIS response but with distinct spatial patterns and magnitudes. Since LBC is strongly
 426 coupled to inversion strength ($\frac{\partial LBC}{\partial EIS} > 0$), these differing EIS responses disrupt the
 427 cloud-temperature relationship across timescales.

428 3. Attribution of Inter-Model Spread: Our decomposition of the cloud feedback equation
 429 reveals that the large inter-model spread in ECS (e.g., between CESM2 and MPI-ESM)
 430 arises primarily from the cloud sensitivity term ($\frac{\partial LCF}{\partial CCF}$) rather than the large-scale
 431 circulation response ($\frac{dCCF}{dT_s}$).

- 432 ○ For MLC, uncertainty is dominated by the parameterized sensitivity to vertical
433 velocity (ω_{700}), reflecting differences in how models couple deep clouds
434 to dynamic ascent 8.
- 435 ○ For UBC, the spread is driven by sensitivities to thermodynamic factors,
436 specifically relative humidity (RH_{700}). Low-ECS models like MPI-ESM
437 severely underestimate the sensitivity of UBC to free-tropospheric moisture,
438 leading to systematic biases in their simulated cloud regimes.
- 439 4. Implications for Model Development: To reduce uncertainty in climate projections,
440 future model development should prioritize improving the physical parameterizations
441 of cloud-turbulence interactions. Specifically, constraining the sensitivity of clouds to
442 dynamic vertical motion and free-tropospheric humidity is critical. Our results suggest
443 that improving the representation of the UBC regime, which is poorly simulated in
444 many current models, offers a promising pathway to narrow the spread in estimated
445 climate sensitivity.

446

447 **Acknowledgments**

448 This work was conducted at the HKUST JC STEM Lab of Convection and Precipitation,
449 supported by the Hong Kong Jockey Club Charities Trust FA123, the Innovation and
450 Technology Commission P0413, the Innovation and Technology Fund P0456 and Research
451 Grants Council 16300823 and 16308924.

452 The authors would like to thank HKUST Fok Ying Tung Research Institute and National
453 Supercomputing Center in Guangzhou Nansha Sub-center for providing high performance
454 computational resources.

455

456 **Open Research**

457 AGU requires an Availability Statement for the underlying data and code needed to
458 understand, evaluate, and build upon the reported research at the time of peer review and
459 publication. Additionally, authors should include an Availability Statement for the software
460 and other research products that have a significant impact on the research. Details and templates
461 are in the Availability Statement section of the Data & Software for Authors Guidance. For
462 physical samples, use the IGSN persistent identifier, see the International Geo Sample
463 Numbers section.

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465 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

466 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

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